

1 **Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: SBK1.**

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6 Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency
7 as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the
8 multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and
9 embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We
10 describe identification of SBK1 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in the human
11 embryonic stem cell.

12 Citations

13 1. van Gorp, P.R., Zhang, J., Liu, J., Tsonaka, R., Mei, H., Dekker, S.O., Bart, C.I., De Coster, T.,
14 Post, H., Heck, A.J. and Schlij, M.J., 2022. Sbk2, a newly discovered atrium-enriched regulator of
15 sarcomere integrity. Circulation Research, 131(1), pp.24-41.